

Forum 1: “Welcome Forum”- Tuesday 3 October

Goals:

- We seek to generate an initial contact between participants and allow them to become familiar with the platform and the tools
- *What motivated you?, What caught your attention? out of all the information you have regarding participation in this project: what did you most like or attracted you?*
- *We would also like you to share the expectations you have regarding your participation in this forum: What do you expect? What do you think it can bring you? And what do you think you can contribute to this experience?*
- *A word that sums up “breakfast” for you.*

During the first two weeks, we will ask participants to describe in the “*Diary Section*” their “*Breakfast Moment*”: Description of the context, What’s breakfast like? Who do they share it with? Where does it take place (home, office, cafe,...)?. Time dedicated to breakfast. What do they have for breakfast? → We will ask them to include photos of their breakfast.

Forum 2: “Meaning of breakfast” – Thursday 5 de October to Thursday 2 November

Thursday 5 October

- *Meaning of breakfast in the context of the family’s diet.*
 - *Breakfast is...*
 - *Qualities associated with breakfast..*
 - *How important is breakfast in your life, in your day-to-day,.. → Expand on the reasons.*
- *What needs does it cover? What do you ask of breakfast?*
 - *Difference between personal breakfast needs and/or those of the rest of the family*

Tuesday 10 October

Description of standard "mid-week" breakfast:

- Contexts where they take place
- Time dedicated to making breakfast and to breakfast itself.
- Who makes breakfast?
- Types of food products: list of products consumed (pastries, juices, yoghurts, breads, milk, biscuits, homemade products,...)
- Where do you buy these products?: they're homemade, shop-bought,...
- Why do you consume these products and not others?

Thursday 12 October

- Type of device (toaster, microwave, frying pan, kettle,...)
- Time available
- Aspects that make it a different experience: the company of your children,....
- Emotions experienced during mid-week breakfast: stress, bonding, enjoyment,... (do not make any suggestions)

Tuesday 17 October

Description of standard "week-end" breakfast:

- Contexts where they take place
- Time dedicated to making breakfast and to breakfast itself.
- Who makes breakfast?
- Types of food products: list of products consumed (pastries, juices, yoghurts, breads, milk, biscuits, homemade products,...)
- Where do you buy these products?: they're homemade, shop-bought,...
- Why do you consume these products and not others?

Thursday 19 October

- Type of device (toaster, microwave, frying pan, kettle,...)
- Time available
- Aspects that make it a different experience: the company of your children,....
- Emotions experienced during week-end breakfast: stress, bonding, enjoyment,... (do not make any suggestions)

Tuesday 24 October

- *Expand further on breakfast and contexts:*
 - *What happens at the office?*
 - *What happens at the cafe?*
 - *What happens at home?*

Thursday 26 October

- *In general, how does the time available affect the type of breakfast you have:*
 - *If you had more time, would your breakfast be different?*
 - *How would that breakfast be?*
 - *Would it affect its quality?*

Tuesday 31 October

- *The best and worst of using these devices (those previously mentioned spontaneously: toaster, microwave, frying pan, kettle, juicer,...)*
 - *Which are indispensable,...*
 - *Real use in everyday life*
 - *How would you like them to be: faster, smaller,...*
 - *Which devices would you like to have and don't have?*

Thursday 2 November

- *The role of "special" food products at breakfast time: lactose-free milk, sugar-free biscuits, gluten-free, wheat-free...*
- *Detailed description of the ideal breakfast: ingredients, products, contexts, brands, location, duration, appliances,...*
 - *Obstacles and drivers that influence the ideal breakfast*

Close with internal survey.

Forum 3: “Breakfast trends” – Tuesday 7 November

Tuesday 7 November

- Identifying breakfast trends: where are we headed, new practices and products, what’s taken into account, integration of new tools,...
- Expanding on the healthy breakfast:
 - Description of what they consider a healthy breakfast: what it includes, types of products, ways of preparing them,...
 - Importance attributed to having a “healthy” breakfast
 - Obstacles and drivers associated with a healthy breakfast
 - Do they believe they have a healthy breakfast: expand on the reasons

Close with internal survey.

Smart Cooking Test

In the Smart Cooking test we will rotate the product presentation, in this way we will learn how each one is valued, and they will all have the same chance of being presented at the beginning or at the end. The presentation will be carried out in the following manner according to country:

<i>Instant dough baker</i>	<i>Sous-vide cooking device</i>	<i>3D food printer</i>
<i>1. Spain</i>	<i>1. UK</i>	<i>1. Germany</i>
<i>2. Germany</i>	<i>2. Spain</i>	<i>2. UK</i>
<i>3. UK</i>	<i>3. Germany</i>	<i>3. Spain</i>

Forum 4: Smart Cooking Test – 1 – Thursday 9 November to 21 November

At the end of the test, a survey will be carried out evaluating the main attributes.

Forum 5: Smart Cooking Test – 2 – Thursday 23 November to 5 December

At the end of the test, a survey will be carried out evaluating the main attributes.

Forum 6: Smart Cooking Test – 2 – Thursday 7 December to 19 December

At the end of the test, a survey will be carried out evaluating the main attributes.

Forum 7: Comparative analysis of the different Smart Cooking tests – Thursday 21 to 31 December

Note: In all cases, we must take into account public holidays where publication will be moved to the day after/before the scheduled date, depending on how the discussion develops. In addition, the last weeks of December are also complicated due to the Christmas holidays. Consider possible extension to the first week of January.